

A Questionnaires Used in the Study

A.1 Digital Profile and XR Exposure Questionnaire

This questionnaire collects demographic information, digital usage patterns, prior exposure to extended reality (XR) technologies, and self-assessed ability to distinguish between AR, VR, and MR environments.

About You

- Email address (institutional).
- Age (numeric entry).
- Gender: Female / Male / Other / Prefer not to say.

Digital Practices

- How often do you use the following? Scale: 1=never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=very often
 - Social media (e.g., TikTok, Instagram, X)
 - E-commerce platforms (e.g., Amazon, Vinted)
 - Online games (e.g., Fortnite, League of Legends)
 - Virtual or augmented reality headsets (e.g., Meta Quest)
- For each of the devices listed below, please indicate your primary activity when using it (single choice per device). Activity categories: Communication and social media / Work and study / Games and entertainment / Online shopping and services / Information and research / Personal creation and management / I do not use this device.
 - Smartphone
 - Tablet
 - Computer
 - Television
 - Radio
 - Game console
- I feel comfortable using digital technologies in my daily life. Scale: 1=disagree, 2=somewhat disagree, 3=somewhat agree, 4=agree

Prior XR Experience

- How often do you use the following? Scale: 1=never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=very often
 - Augmented Reality (AR)
 - Mixed Reality (MR)
 - Virtual Reality (VR)
- I feel capable of explaining the difference between AR, VR, and MR. Scale: 1=disagree, 2=somewhat disagree, 3=somewhat agree, 4=agree
- (conditional) Please explain the difference between AR, VR, and MR in a few sentences (open-ended)

A.2 Invisible Risk Perception and Emotional Response Questionnaire

Participants complete this questionnaire after each intervention (VR baseline, Alex, Kelly, and lecture). This repeated-measures instrument captures immediate cognitive and emotional responses to invisible risk mechanisms within each mediation context.

General Invisible Risk Perception

- Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. Scale: 1=disagree, 2=somewhat disagree, 3=neutral, 4=somewhat agree, 5=agree
 - In general, interactive systems act primarily in the user’s best interest.
 - In general, interactive systems function as black boxes for the user.
 - In general, interactive systems provide all necessary information for users to make informed decisions.
 - In general, interactive systems limit the user’s ability to act according to their own intentions.
 - In general, users can freely ignore or refuse suggestions from interactive systems.
 - In general, interactive systems induce discomfort (stress, anxiety, unease).

VR-Specific Invisible Risk Perception The same items are contextually adapted to refer to: - the VR system just experienced (baseline), - the VR system used by Alex or Kelly (storyboards), - VR systems in general (lecture).

Doubt and Moral Unease (open-ended)

- Was there a moment when you doubted the intentions of the VR system? Please describe.
- Was there a moment when you experienced moral unease regarding the VR system? Please describe.

Emotional Response

- To what extent did you experience the following emotions while engaging with the VR system / Alex’s scenario / Kelly’s scenario / the lecture? Emotional intensity scale: 1=never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always
 - Surprise
 - Sadness
 - Disgust
 - Fear
 - Happiness
 - Anger
- Which emotion did you feel most strongly? Why? (open-ended)

A.3 VR Literacy Assessment Questionnaire

Participants complete this questionnaire after the closing lecture. This instrument constitutes a central contribution of the study, as it operationalizes VR literacy through two risk awareness and skill acquisition.

Risk Awareness

- Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. Scale: 1=disagree, 2=somewhat disagree, 3=somewhat agree, 4=agree
 - Some scenarios made me reflect on invisible risks.
 - I identified risks I had never considered before this course.
 - This course showed me how systems influence users without their knowledge.
 - I am now more attentive to invisible risks in my daily life.
- For each statement above to which you responded “somewhat agree” or “agree,” please elaborate on your answer.
- For each statement above to which you responded “somewhat disagree” or “disagree,” please elaborate on your answer.

Skill Acquisition

- Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. Scale: 1=disagree, 2=somewhat disagree, 3=somewhat agree, 4=agree
 - This course helped me better understand invisible risks (e.g., algorithms, nudges).
 - I feel capable of recognizing signs that a system is trying to manipulate me.
 - I feel capable of explaining invisible risks associated with digital systems.
 - I know how to act to protect myself from invisible risks.
- For each statement above to which you responded “somewhat agree” or “agree,” please elaborate on your answer.
- For each statement above to which you responded “somewhat disagree” or “disagree,” please elaborate on your answer.

B General Digital Risk Perceptions (Additional Figure)

Fig. I presents the distributions for general invisible risk perceptions (“interactive systems in general”) across interventions.

Fig. I. Distribution of general invisible risk perceptions across interventions.